

Electron-beam exposure as a defect passivation strategy for HfO₂/InGaAs field-effect devices

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Abstract:

HfO₂/InGaAs gate stacks are promising for both next-generation CMOS electronics and integrated photonic devices, where highly doped InGaAs layers (10^{18} - 10^{19} cm⁻³) enable efficient carrier accumulation in MOS structures. However, the high density of electrically active defects at the oxide/semiconductor interface severely limits device performance due to Fermi level pinning. Here we demonstrate that controlled electron-beam (e-beam) exposure can act as an effective defect-engineering strategy for HfO₂/InGaAs interfaces. By combining capacitance-voltage measurements with numerical modeling accounting for both interface states and border traps, we show that e-beam irradiation significantly modifies defect distributions and enables partial interface passivation within a defined electron dose window. MOS capacitors based on Al/HfO₂ (35 nm)/InGaAs (150 nm, $n \sim 10^{19}$ cm⁻³) were fabricated after controlled e-beam exposure, allowing systematic extraction of defect-

state densities and charge profiles in the highly doped semiconductor layer. Complementary MOSFET devices fabricated by e-beam lithography confirm the impact on electrical performance. These results establish e-beam exposure as a practical approach for simultaneous defect passivation and nanoscale patterning in HfO₂/InGaAs devices, offering a pathway toward simplified fabrication of advanced CMOS and integrated photonic technologies.

1. Introduction

III–V compound semiconductors have attracted growing interest as alternatives to silicon for next-generation CMOS (Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor) technologies, particularly in scaled MOSFET (Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor) architectures [1]. Their intrinsically low effective mass leads to enhanced carrier mobility, enabling superior transport properties that support high-frequency operation as well as reduced supply voltages for low-power applications [1,2]. In advanced device architectures, different regions typically involve distinct doping levels, ranging from moderately doped channels to highly doped contact or access layers, also reaching carrier concentrations in the 10¹⁸ - 10¹⁹ cm⁻³ range [3–5].

In this framework, HfO₂ deposited by atomic layer deposition (ALD) has emerged as one of the most promising gate dielectric candidates for In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As channels due to its high dielectric constant and compatibility with scaling requirements [6–9]. Beyond CMOS logic, HfO₂/InGaAs interfaces are also attracting increasing attention in optoelectronic and photonic devices, including MOS-based electro-optic modulators and integrated photonic platforms. In these systems, highly doped InGaAs layers (typically 10¹⁸ - 10¹⁹ cm⁻³) enable efficient carrier accumulation in MOS phase shifters, allowing modulation of the optical refractive index and high-speed electro-optic operation [10–13].

Despite these advantages, the integration of HfO₂ with InGaAs remains limited by the high density of electrically active defects at the oxide/semiconductor interface. These defects strongly degrade device performance by inducing severe Fermi level pinning, which hinders inversion-mode operation [14]. Extensive studies have investigated the physical origin of these defects, generally distinguishing between interface states and border traps. Interface states are located on the semiconductor side of the interface and are typically associated with midgap states, whereas border traps are localized within the near-interfacial layers of the oxide [15,16].

Several passivation strategies have been proposed to mitigate these defects in HfO₂/InGaAs systems, including (NH₄)₂S surface treatments to remove native oxides [17,18], forming gas annealing to reduce interface state density [19], plasma-assisted nitridation [20], and oxygen scavenging layers [21]. Although effective, these approaches generally increase process complexity, cost, and fabrication time, motivating the exploration of alternative strategies that can be integrated directly within device fabrication flows.

In this work, we investigate direct electron-beam (e-beam) exposure as a strategy to reduce defect states and improve the electrical behavior of HfO₂/InGaAs MOS structures. Energetic electrons are known to induce structural and electronic modifications in dielectric layers and semiconductor interfaces [22,23], suggesting that e-beam irradiation may alter the defect landscape of oxide/semiconductor heterostructures. However, the impact of controlled e-beam exposure on high-k/III-V interfaces has not yet been systematically investigated.

Here we show that controlled e-beam exposure significantly modifies the density and distribution of defect states in HfO₂/InGaAs gate stacks, enabling partial passivation of the oxide/semiconductor

interface within a defined electron dose window. Defect-state distributions are quantified by fitting capacitance-voltage (C-V) characteristics measured on MOS capacitors using a properly developed model to account for both interface states and border traps. These defects produce characteristic deviations from the ideal response: midgap interface states generate the inversion hump even at low frequencies, while border traps induce the frequency dispersion observed in accumulation due to carrier tunneling into near-interfacial oxide states with long time constants determined by their distance from the interface [24,25]. To experimentally investigate these effects, Al/HfO₂(35 nm)/InGaAs (150 nm, $n \sim 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) MOS structures are fabricated after exposing the material stack to controlled electron doses, enabling systematic comparison of defect-state distributions obtained from numerical simulations of the measured C-V characteristics. The analysis also provides charge density profiles in the highly doped InGaAs layer ($10^{18} - 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) as a function of gate bias, revealing how e-beam exposure affects carrier modulation at the oxide/semiconductor interface. Moreover, to further assess the robustness of the defect-state model and to correlate electrical behavior with device performance, MOSFET devices are fabricated on the same material stack using e-beam lithography (EBL) and characterized through current-voltage (I-V) measurements combined with numerical simulations.

The impact of e-beam exposure is technologically relevant because it can be naturally and controllably integrated into existing fabrication flows. In large-area photonic integrated circuits, where optical lithography is used to define waveguides and electro-optic modulators, a preliminary e-beam step could passivate the HfO₂/InGaAs interface prior to patterning. Conversely, nanoscale devices such as aggressively scaled III-V MOSFETs and compact MOS electro-optic modulators are typically fabricated by EBL, where the e-beam itself used for patterning may also induce defect passivation by tailoring properly the exposure dose according to the specific kind and thickness of the resists film used. By identifying the electron dose window that enables effective interface passivation without degrading device functionality, this work proposes e-beam irradiation as a practical defect-engineering step in HfO₂/InGaAs gate stacks, enabling patterning and interface passivation in a single step, and paving the way toward simplified fabrication of advanced CMOS and integrated photonic devices.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Fabrication of the MOS structures

The schematic of the material stack is reported in Fig.1a. A 35 nm-thick HfO₂ layer was deposited by ALD on top of the 150 nm-thick heavily n-doped In_{0.52}Ga_{0.47}As layer ($n_0 = 8.8 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The InGaAs layer was grown by metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) on top of a lightly n-doped InP substrate. On the bottom of the sample, the backside ohmic contact was fabricated by depositing a 50 nm-thick Ni layer by e-beam evaporation followed by thermal evaporation of a 50 nm-thick Au layer.

To evaluate the effect of e-beam exposure, selected areas on the top surface of the sample were irradiated with different electron doses. To restrict the exposure to isolated areas of the sample, a mechanical shadow mask was placed in direct contact with the sample surface. The shadow mask featured circular apertures with a diameter of 350 μm (Fig.1b). Selected apertures were used to define the areas subjected to e-beam exposure and subsequent metal evaporation for MOS device fabrication, with the exposure performed using an EBL system. One aperture was left unexposed to serve as a reference and the resulting MOS device is referred to as DOT000. The other apertures were exposed to increasing electron doses of 100, 300, and 600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, referred as DOT100, DOT300,

and DOT600 devices, respectively. Following e-beam exposure, and without removing or shifting the shadow mask, gate electrodes were deposited by thermal evaporation of a 60 nm thick Al film (Fig. 1c). The resulting self-aligned gate electrodes appeared as circular dots, perfectly overlapping the irradiated HfO₂ areas (Fig. 1d).

FIGURE 1. Fabrication flow of MOS devices. (a) Schematic of the material stack: HfO₂ (35 nm)/InGaAs (150 nm)/InP with Ni (50 nm)/Au (50 nm) layer as backside ohmic contact. (b) Circular areas defined by 350 μm -diameter apertures of a shadow mask were uniformly exposed to e-beam (50 kV, 21.8 nA) at doses of 100, 300, and 600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. (c) A 60 nm-thick Al gate electrode was deposited by thermal evaporation without removing the shadow mask. (d) Schematic of the fabricated MOS devices with 350 μm -diameter circular gate electrodes.

2.2. Electrical characterization of MOS devices

The MOS devices described in the previous section have been electrically characterized by acquiring capacitance-voltage (C-V) characteristics. The measurements were performed on DOT000, DOT100, DOT300, and DOT600 devices using an impedance analyzer at room temperature and in the frequency range of 200 Hz - 100 kHz with an AC amplitude of 100 mV. Fig. 2a-d show selected normalized C-V (C/C_0) curves measured at 200 Hz, 1 kHz, 10 kHz, and 100 kHz for each MOS device, where C_0 denotes the theoretical oxide capacitance given by $C_0 = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r A / d$, with ϵ_0 the vacuum dielectric constant, ϵ_r the relative dielectric constant of the HfO₂ = 18, A the circular gate electrode area and d the HfO₂ thickness (35 nm). All devices display a clear capacitance modulation with gate bias, reflecting the change in carrier density within the heavily doped InGaA layer close to the HfO₂ interface. For positive gate bias, all MOS devices operate in accumulation regime, and the capacitance approaches the oxide capacitance, as expected.

As the gate bias is swept toward negative values, the devices enter the depletion regime, where the capacitance progressively decreases due to the series combination of the oxide capacitance, the depletion capacitance, and an additional capacitance associated to the charge introduced by defect states. Upon further reduction of the gate bias, the capacitance reaches a minimum, corresponding to the transition from depletion to inversion, at approximately -1 V for DOT000 and -3 V for DOT100, DOT300, and DOT600.

The maximum capacitance modulation, defined as the difference between the value at +6 V and the minimum capacitance at -1 V for DOT000 and -3 V for DOT100, DOT300 and DOT600, progressively decreases from $\sim 0.10 C_0$ for DOT000 to $\sim 0.06 C_0$ for DOT600 by increasing e-beam exposure dose. This behavior is commonly attributed to a high density of defect states, which gives rise to an additional interface state capacitance in series with the oxide capacitance, thereby increasing the minimum measured capacitance.

Consistently, defect states are evident in all C-V characteristics. In particular, a clear signature of a high density of border traps is provided by the frequency-dependent dispersion observed under positive gate bias in the accumulation regime. By contrast, the frequency dependence of the capacitance under negative gate bias is primarily associated with interface states. At low frequencies, the minority-carrier generation-recombination dynamics at the interface are sufficiently fast to follow the AC excitation, enabling modulation of the inversion charge density and resulting in a large differential capacitance that drives the total MOS capacitance toward the oxide capacitance. At high frequencies, unlike the ideal MOS response in which the capacitance remains pinned at its minimum value, an increase in capacitance is still observed, although with a smaller slope compared to the low-frequency case. This high-frequency inversion hump is commonly regarded as a hallmark of a high density of interface states. Finally, the progressive shift of the capacitance minimum toward more negative gate voltages observed for devices exposed to increasing electron-beam doses is attributed to e-beam-induced localized charge at the interface, as well as to dose-dependent variations in the density of interface defect states participating in carrier generation-recombination processes.

FIGURE 2. Experimental normalized C-V characteristics (C/C_0) measured on circular MOS devices ($350\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter) (a) unexposed and exposed to electron doses of (b) 100, (c) 300, and (d) $600\ \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. For each device, C-V curves acquired using AC excitation frequencies of 200 Hz (green), 1 kHz (gold), 10 kHz (orange), and 100 kHz (red) with an amplitude of 100 mV are shown. C_0 is the theoretical oxide capacitance.

2.3. Numerical simulations

The presence of interface states and border traps was accounted for in the simulations by introducing a trap density of states (DOS) spatially distributed within the oxide in proximity to the oxide/semiconductor interface. The gate dielectric layer was modeled as a semiconductor with a wide bandgap, assumed to be 2 eV larger than that of InGaAs. This modeling choice is primarily dictated by technical limitations of the simulation program, which does not allow the inclusion of acceptor and/or donor trap states in regions defined as “ideal” oxides, thereby precluding the simulation of border trap effects when the HfO_2 region is treated as such. On the other hand, a band offset of this magnitude effectively suppresses thermionic injection of electrons and holes from InGaAs into the conduction and valence bands of the wider bandgap semiconductor and thus provides a suitable approach for modeling HfO_2 in the presence of border traps. In the simulations, a non-local tunneling model has been enabled, allowing trap states within the oxide to exchange carriers with those in the conduction and valence bands of InGaAs at the interface through capture and emission processes. The spatial distribution of the trap states was described by a Gaussian profile centered at the oxide/semiconductor interface and extending exclusively into the dielectric layer side, with a standard

deviation of 4 nm. The energetic distribution of the trap states was extracted by assuming an analytical form for the density of states (DOS), modeled as the superposition of an exponential and a Gaussian distribution. The parameters of this DOS energy distribution were then determined through a best-fit procedure aimed at reproducing the measured C–V characteristics.

The fitting strategy was specifically aimed at reproducing as accurately as possible the C-V curves measured at the lowest frequency, thereby ensuring that the extracted DOS incorporates the contribution of traps with longer capture and emission time constants. This approach enables the use of the resulting DOS as a reliable input for the simulation of MOSFET conductance characteristics, which were experimentally obtained under DC conditions.

It is important to note that the DOS values obtained from C-V fitting should not be interpreted as a physically unique or fully accurate determination. As discussed in Caruso et al. [26], different assumptions regarding the microscopic parameters of trap states or the capture and emission processes, such as cross sections or tunneling effective masses, can lead to different DOS profiles that nonetheless reproduce the measured C-V characteristics with comparable accuracy. A rigorous determination of these microscopic parameters lies beyond the scope of this work. Despite this intrinsic ambiguity, the analysis carried out here provides meaningful insights, as the primary focus is on the variation of the DOS as a function of irradiation dose rather than on the absolute values of the extracted parameters.

Fig. 3a shows a comparison between the experimental and simulated normalized C-V characteristics of the DOT000 device for four selected AC frequencies. The overall agreement between experiments and simulations confirms the validity of the modelling approach adopted to describe and quantify the defect states in this heterostructure. As can be observed, the agreement between the C-V curve measured at 200 Hz and the corresponding simulated characteristic is nearly perfect. At higher frequencies, both the experimental data and the simulations exhibit clear signatures of a significant density of border traps: in fact, in the accumulation regime (gate bias $\gg 0$), the capacitance shows a pronounced frequency dispersion, decreasing as the frequency increases [24]. In the inversion regime (gate bias $\ll 0$), a noticeable increase in capacitance for decreasing bias is observed even at high frequencies, whereas devices with ideal interfaces would remain at the minimum capacitance level as mentioned before. It is apparent that at higher frequencies and under inversion conditions (gate bias $\ll 0$), the agreement between measurements and simulations remains mainly qualitative, with the simulated capacitance values consistently lying below the experimental results.

This behavior suggests that the actual spatial and energetic distribution of border traps is likely more complex than the simplified representation adopted in the present model, which nevertheless reproduces the experimental trends with good accuracy. A simultaneous fitting of both low- and high-frequency C-V characteristics can partially reduce this discrepancy; however, this comes at the expense of a reduced accuracy in the low-frequency regime. In this work, priority has been intentionally given to the most accurate possible reproduction of the low-frequency C-V characteristics, since these also include the contribution of slower trap states and therefore provide the most comprehensive information on the evolution of the defect distribution. Hence, the modeling has not been intended to reproduce every detail of the experimental C-V response across the entire frequency range, but rather to provide a consistent and physically meaningful description of the evolution of the density of states (DOS) as a function of electron dose. In this perspective, the adoption of a relatively simple analytical form for the trap-state distribution optimized on the low frequency C-V is advantageous, as it enables a more direct and robust comparison among devices subjected to different irradiation conditions.

For the DOT100, DOT300, and DOT600 devices, Fig. 3b reports only the experimental and simulated curves acquired at 200 Hz, corresponding to the lowest measurement frequency and thus capturing the largest population of responding defect states. As can be observed, at this frequency, used as the fitting target, the agreement between simulations and experimental data is nearly perfect.

Figure 3c reports the DOS at HfO₂/InGaAs interface extracted from the fitting procedure for the different irradiation doses. The distributions consist of an acceptor-like component located in the upper portion of the bandgap and a donor-like component situated at lower energies. For both branches, the adopted functional form for the DOS combines an exponential tail with a Gaussian contribution. The fitting procedure, however, assigns significant weight to the Gaussian terms only for the acceptor states, placing their peaks at energies above the conduction band edge of InGaAs.

The donor-like portion of the DOS exhibits only minor variations with irradiation, indicating a negligible sensitivity to the applied dose. In contrast, the acceptor-like states show a strong dependence on irradiation. In particular, for doses on the order of 100 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, a marked reduction in the density of acceptor states is observed within the energy range corresponding to the InGaAs bandgap, i.e., the portion of the DOS that governs the interface behavior under practically relevant bias conditions between -6 V and +6 V. This reduction results in an enhanced field-effect modulation capability of the interface.

The impact of this behavior is further illustrated in Fig. 3d, which presents the simulated electron density profiles near the interface for bias conditions of -4 V and +4 V at different irradiation doses. The sample irradiated at 100 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ exhibits a significantly stronger response to the applied electric field, as evidenced by the more pronounced variation in the electron density profile when bias changes from -4 V to +4 V. The analysis also reveals that 100 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ is an optimal irradiation dose for minimizing acceptor-like trap states: in fact, at 300 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, the acceptor DOS returns to values comparable to those of the non-irradiated device, while at 600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ the trap density exceeds the initial level. This trend is consistently reflected in the corresponding electron density profiles shown in Fig. 3d.

FIGURE 3. a) Normalized C-V characteristics (C/C_0) of the unexposed MOS device (DOT000), comparing simulated results (solid lines) with experimental data (symbols) acquired at different frequencies. b) Normalized C-V characteristics (C/C_0) of MOS devices subjected to different irradiation doses, showing simulations (solid lines) and measurements (symbols) at a frequency of 200 Hz. c) Extracted density of interface states at the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}$ interface ($x = 0 \mu\text{m}$), obtained by fitting the 200 Hz C-V characteristics of irradiated MOS devices. d) Electron density distribution in the InGaAs layer in proximity to the HfO_2 interface ($x = 0 \mu\text{m}$), evaluated at gate biases of +4 V (solid lines) and -4 V (dashed lines).

2.4. MOSFET fabrication and characterization

To experimentally validate that the defect-state theoretical model accurately captures both the qualitative and quantitative impact of defects and reliably predicts the electrical behavior and performance of the devices, MOSFETs were fabricated on the same material stack and characterized through current–voltage (I–V) measurements in combination with numerical device simulations. Fig. 4 reports the geometry and the electrical characterization of the fabricated devices. The device layout consists of a gate (G) electrode formed by a Ti (20 nm)/Au (40 nm) stack deposited on the HfO_2 dielectric layer, while the drain (D) and source (S) contacts, realized by Ti (10 nm)/Au (80 nm), are deposited directly on the InGaAs surface after dry etching of HfO_2 layer. A schematic top and side view of the device structure are shown in the top and bottom panel of Fig. 4a, respectively, while Fig. 4b presents scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of a representative device.

The experimental transfer characteristics in the subthreshold regime, expressed as relative variation of the drain current with respect to its maximum value ($I_{DS}/I_{DS,max}$) versus gate bias (V_{GS}) at $V_{DS} = 5$ mV, for a representative MOSFET (50 μm gate width, 53 μm channel length) is shown in Fig. 4c. The observed modulation of the normalized drain current is of the order of 4%. The inset displays the drain current (I_{DS}) versus drain-source bias (V_{DS}) characteristics showing the expected linear behavior.

This experimental relative variation of the drain current I_{DS} can be compared with the corresponding simulated relative variation of the total electron density per unit area in the MOSFET channel ($\rho_e = \int n dx$ where n is the electron density and x is the coordinate in the direction of the depth of the channel, see fig. 3d), since, at low V_{DS} , drain current and total charge density are proportional. Figure 4d shows the evolution of this quantity, normalized to its value at $V_{GS} = 4$ V. As can be observed, the trend is qualitatively very similar, both in shape and in order of magnitude thereby providing an indirect validation of the approach adopted for the DOS estimation. It is also worth noting that the measurements in Fig. 4c were performed under DC conditions, making the comparison with a DOS extracted from low-frequency C-V fitting particularly meaningful.

FIGURE 4. a) Schematic top (upper) and side (lower) views of the MOSFET device, comprising the gate (G) electrode formed by Ti (20 nm)/Au (40 nm) deposited on the HfO_2 layer, and drain (D) and source (S) contacts realized by Ti (10 nm)/Au (80 nm) deposited on the InGaAs surface. b) SEM images of a representative MOSFET device at three different magnifications, with the highest-magnification image acquired at a 42° tilt angle. The same device is used for the electrical characterization shown in panel (c). c) Experimental transfer

characteristics in the subthreshold regime, reported as relative drain current ($I_{DS}/I_{DS,max}$) versus gate bias (V_{GS}) measured at $V_{DS} = 5$ mV for one representative MOSFET device with a 50 μm - wide gate placed in a 53 μm D-S gap. In the inset, drain current (I_{DS}) versus drain - source bias (V_{DS}) characteristic at different gate bias ($V_{GS}=-4\text{V}$ and $V_{GS}=4\text{V}$). d) Gate-voltage dependence of the simulated total electron density per unit area (ρ_e see text), normalized to its value at $V_g = 4$ V.

These results demonstrate the model's validity at an exposure of 300 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, confirming that the electron-beam treatment effectively passivates interface defects even under standard lithographic conditions. The EBL passivation strategy can be further optimized by reducing the exposure dose to a target of 100 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ by employing specific high-sensitivity resists and dedicated fabrication processes.

3. Conclusions

In this work, the impact of electron irradiation on the passivation of border traps in $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}$ interfaces has been systematically investigated. The analysis has been carried out through low-frequency C-V measurements on MOS structures subjected to irradiation doses ranging from 0 to 600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. An optimal irradiation dose has been identified, at which a substantial reduction of acceptor-like trap states is achieved, resulting in interfaces with a significantly enhanced sensitivity to the applied electric field. The extracted DOS has been further validated by comparing to drain current measurements performed on MOSFET devices.

The observed improvements highlight the effectiveness of electron irradiation as a viable technique for interface engineering in advanced semiconductor devices. From a technological standpoint, the use of EBL as the irradiation source is particularly appealing, as it relies on equipment that is already widely available within standard microfabrication toolchains. This approach enables simultaneous nanoscale patterning and interface passivation within a single step, reducing fabrication complexity, time, and cost while providing a practical route to improve the performance of III-V MOS devices for both advanced FETs and integrated photonic platforms.

4. Methods

Material growth.

$\text{In}_{0.52}\text{Ga}_{0.47}\text{As}$ thin film is grown by MOCVD on slightly doped InP substrate ($n=10^{17}$ cm^{-3}). For MOS devices, the InGaAs layer thickness was 150 nm, whereas a 20 nm-thick InGaAs film was used for MOSFET fabrication. The InGaAs layers were Si-doped, resulting in a doping level of 8.8×10^{18} cm^{-3} . For samples used in MOSFET fabrication only, a 20 nm-thick AlInAs layer was grown by MOCVD between the InP substrate and the InGaAs layer to act as an electrical barrier. A 35 nm-thick HfO_2 dielectric layer was subsequently deposited on top of the InGaAs layer by ALD.

MOS and MOSFET fabrication.

The MOS devices consist of circular Al gate electrodes (60 nm-thick) thermally evaporated onto the HfO_2 surface using a shadow mask with circular apertures of 350 μm in diameter, spaced 2 mm apart. Prior to metal deposition, the sample areas under the mask apertures were either left unexposed or irradiated with an e-beam at doses of 100, 300, and 600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ using an EBL system (Raith VOYAGER), employing a beam current of 21.8 nA and an acceleration voltage of 50 kV.

A backside ohmic contact was formed by depositing a 50 nm-thick Ni layer by e-beam evaporation, followed by thermal evaporation of a 50 nm-thick Au layer.

The MOSFET devices were fabricated using a multistep EBL process with successive realignment and lift-off steps. In the first lithographic step, the gate electrodes were defined by patterning a 600 nm-thick PMMA 650K resist using an electron dose of 300 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. After development in a 1:2 methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK):isopropanol (IPA) solution, Ti (20 nm)/Au (40 nm) gate metals were deposited by e-beam evaporation, followed by 1stripping in acetone. The gate layout consists of repeated sets of rectangular gates with a fixed length of 390 μm and five different widths of 100, 50, 10, 5, and 1 μm . Each gate terminates into two electrical pads with lateral dimensions of 90 $\mu\text{m} \times 90 \mu\text{m}$.

In the second fabrication step, device mesas were defined by reactive ion etching (RIE) of the 35 nm-thick HfO_2 layer using a CF_4 -based plasma, followed by wet etching of the InGaAs layer in a diluted $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:1:50) solution. A 100 nm-thick Al layer, patterned by EBL, was used as a hard mask for both etching steps and subsequently removed by selective wet etching.

The third and fourth lithographic steps were dedicated to the fabrication of the drain and source contacts. First, rectangular openings of 300 $\mu\text{m} \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ were defined in the HfO_2 layer by RIE using a 100 nm-thick Al hard mask. After removal of the Al layer, the drain and source contacts were fabricated by patterning a 600 nm-thick PMMA 650K resist with an electron dose of 300 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, followed by development in a 1:2 MIBK:IPA solution, Ti (10 nm)/Au (80 nm) e-beam evaporation, and lift-off in acetone. The resulting drain and source contacts are rectangular (310 $\mu\text{m} \times 210 \mu\text{m}$) and are separated from the gate by channel lengths ranging from 95 to 1.5 μm (95, 45, 18, 8, 4, and 1.5 μm), depending on the device geometry.

Electrical characterization:

The MOS devices were electrically characterized by means of I-V and C-V measurements. The backside contact was made by attaching the sample onto a copper foil using silver paste. Micro-probes were used to contact the Cu foil and the top metal electrodes of the MOS capacitors to perform two-terminal electrical measurements. Leakage current characterization was performed on reference devices (DOT000) using a DC voltage (Keithley 6517B) source and a picoammeter (Keithley 6485). The resulting I-V curve was used to define the safe operating voltage range, identified as $\pm 6 \text{ V}$, within which the leakage current remains below 100 nA. C-V measurements were carried out using an LCR meter (Keysight E4980AL) with AC excitation frequencies ranging from 200 Hz to 100 kHz and an amplitude of 100 mV.

MOSFET devices were characterized through C-V measurements and gate leakage current (I_G) measurements by sweeping the gate-source voltage (V_{GS}) within a safe operating range of $\pm 4 \text{ V}$. The subthreshold characteristics of the devices were measured by acquiring the transfer curves (I_{DS} vs. V_{GS}) of the devices at V_{DS} ranging between -5 mV and +5 mV.

Numerical simulation:

The simulations were carried out using the Synopsys TCAD software package, adopting a one-dimensional (1D) approach for the device structure. The presence of border traps was accounted for by modeling the insulating layer as a semiconductor characterized by a bandgap significantly wider than that of InGaAs. Tunneling mechanisms toward traps were enabled, considering both their spatial and energetic distributions within the modeled semiconductor region. The calibration of the model parameters was performed using the MATLAB optimization routines, specifically the “lsqnonlin” function, employing the “trust-region-reflective” algorithm.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Data availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available using the following digital object identifier:

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